

Theological Reflection

THE HEART OF A TRUE ASHRAM A Train Encounter

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Abstract: This pastoral reflection draws from a serendipitous train conversation in Maharashtra and a pastoral encounter after Sunday Mass in Nagpur to explore the essence of an authentic *ashram* – Hindu or Christian – as rooted not in buildings or institutions but in the living presence of holiness and the radical formation of saints. Invoking the vision of contemplative silence born of inner exigence and divine fullness of Fr. Jules Monchanin (Swami Parama Arubi Ananda), it calls communities to prioritize sanctity over efficiency, offering quiet witness in a noisy world hungry for authentic divine encounter.

Keywords: Christian *Ashram*, Holiness, Contemplative Silence, Interreligious Dialogue, Jules Monchanin, Swami Parama Arubi Ananda.

INTRODUCTION

There is something unique about travelling in Indian trains—one gets to experience serendipitous encounters whose memory lingers in the mind. Our railways afford a sort of diversity, intellectual and otherwise, despite

all the difficulties and discomfort associated with train travel in India.

On a recent five-hour journey through Maharashtra, I found myself among seven learned, strongly opinionated men. Our conversation, though chaotic, was rich. At one point, we spoke about schools, and I was pleased to hear the positive impression these men held of Christian-run institutions. Someone raised the question of a well-known school in Nagpur, part of a cluster of charitable institutions founded by someone popularly regarded as a *sant* (in Hinduism, a saint or holy person)—a modern-day Shankaracharya. This school was established as part of his *ashram*, aimed at uplifting the poor and needy sections of society.

With the saintly founder long deceased, one traveller asked: “Who manages that place now?”

“A trust—an NGO,” came the reply.

The objection was swift: “But how can you call it an *ashram* without a *sant*? An *ashram* is not just a building. Without that presence, it is just an institution.”

1. THE ESSENCE OF AN *ASHRAM*

The reasoning was striking and sobering. It raised an essential question: What constitutes an *ashram*? Not the physical infrastructure, not the charitable works, not even organizational efficiency—but the presence of the holy, the commitment of those surrendered to God’s transformation of human souls. This is not romanticism; such presence is not ornamental. Without it, an institution – no matter how excellent its facilities or sound its administration – remains merely bricks and mortar.

What struck me most forcefully was that this principle emerges from Hindu spiritual tradition itself. The traveller’s objection was a call to fidelity from within his own tradition, yet it resonates with our Christian understanding of religious life: authenticity requires holiness; institutions without animating presence are dead.

That question lingered with me. It echoed a recent Sunday encounter. After Holy Mass, a non-Christian couple approached me, anguished over their eight-year-old son enrolled in a Catholic school. They chose it deliberately in the hope of shielding him from what they called “superstitious influences” in their milieu, seeking sound humanistic – if not explicitly Christian – education amid a sea of prevalent options. Instead, the mother lamented the school’s indistinguishability from countless secular counterparts: run “just like any other,” adrift in a “mentality of accommodation” that honours every trend and every sort of spiritual practice with equal enthusiasm—the very chaos they sought to escape. Where, they asked, is the distinctive Catholic mark?

2. PRIORITIZING SOULS OVER SYSTEMS

Consider the implications for those of us who claim to live within Christian *ashrams*—whether friaries, convents, monasteries, or something else. An *ashram* exists for a singular purpose: to nurture holiness, to shape human beings into saints. Not perfect people or those without struggle, but individuals so given to God, so radically committed to the evangelical counsels, so transformed by contemplation and prayer, that they become living witnesses to the supernatural in a world grown deaf to it.

Yet this vision is fragile. If an *ashram* prioritizes anything else – running schools, managing property or maintaining charitable operations – without producing saints or labouring for the transformation of souls, it has ceased to be an *ashram*, regardless of who administers it. An *ashram* flourishes through uncompromising commitment to forming holy people, not through structures or governance alone.

3. A QUIET WITNESS

But what does such sanctity look like? Not always dramatic heroism or public renown, but the quiet witness of a human

being living with intention: sitting alone in stillness, absorbed in the mysteries of faith rather than in distraction, counter-culturally attentive to inner work and ordered love. Fr. Jules Monchanin of the archdiocese of Lyon (1895–1957), who took the name Swami Parama Arubi Ananda (“Bliss of the Supreme Spirit”), suggested that a Christian *ashram* should be, above all, a place where the Gospel message is contemplated in reverent silence—a silence motivated not by any rule but by inner need and divine abundance. It is a place where faces radiate inner peace and joy because they live the Gospel with intense, undivided love.¹

This is the power of the Christian *ashram*: it testifies to a world addicted to noise that another way of being is possible—not through preaching alone, but through the simple presence of those who have chosen differently. In such encounters, nothing is preached formally, yet everything is witnessed. The Name of Jesus emerges not as a doctrine to debate, but as a power to invoke. This is the fruitfulness of a presence: a space where individual holiness becomes a beacon to those who hunger for transcendence in a forgetful world.

CONCLUSION: AN INVITATION TO FIDELITY

Those of us who seek to foster sanctity – whether in our religious houses, parishes, families, schools, or friendships – need to ask ourselves searching questions: Are we truly helping those around us to devote themselves to prayer? Are we guiding them towards freedom from self-seeking and kindling in them the fire of charity that burns to serve God and save souls? And does this mission flow from lives transformed by contemplation—lives in which God’s presence is palpable, where those committed to Christ surrender with such totality that their very existence becomes a word spoken to the world? Consider your own community: is it fostering the transformation of souls into

¹ Jules Monchanin [Swāmi Paramārubbyānandam], *Mystique de l’Inde, mystère chrétien* (Paris: Librarie Arthème Fayard, 1974, 1974), esp. 199.

the likeness of Christ, or has it drifted into good works without the animating fire of holiness? What would it mean to recover, with fresh urgency, the conviction that sanctity – not efficiency, reputation, or institutional stability – is the true measure of our fidelity?

The world hungers for witnesses: not perfect people, but those so radically devoted to God that their presence alone speaks of another world. Every true *ashram* exists to produce saints.

Book Reviews

Book Review Editor: Anil D'Almeida SJ

Social Witness of a Martyr: The Collected Writings of Rani Maria. By Jessy Thomas Karachira FCC. ISBN 978-93-94507-99-9. Delhi: Media House, 2026. Pp. 394. Price: ₹ 550.

This book presents the authentic writings of Blessed Martyr Rani Maria (1954–1995), accompanied by interpretations and reflections by Jessy Thomas Karachira, FCC. It seeks to highlight “the strenuous effort of Rani Maria to integrate her prayer life with her apostolic activities, the spirituality she lived by, and her involvement with the local communities she served, along with her underlying pastoral and missionary choices” (pp. 29–30). Having successfully defended her doctoral thesis, titled *Rani Maria FCC: The Edition of the Writings and the Prayers Collectio – A Source of a Social Spirituality*, at the Pontifical University of

Antonianum, Rome, in 2023, Karachira now publishes the fruit of her research in two parts. *Social Witness of a Martyr* is the first volume and contains the primary sources of her research. It demonstrates that Rani Maria’s “activity was not just about doing” and confirms her “social mysticism... the spirituality of a social activist” (pp. 17–18).

Karachira acknowledges that “this book was part of God’s dream to share the extraordinary story of Blessed Rani Maria with the world” (p. 13). In the Foreword, Giuseppe Buffon, the moderator of the research, affirms that Rani Maria’s work was “not merely about welfare.” He notes that “to read her activity within her writings is to go in search of the thought behind her action, to set out in search of the ‘why’ and the ‘inspiration’ of her decisions. It is to say that her service was not just doing!” (p. 17).